

A compact triband patch antenna design at terahertz frequencies

Youssef Amraoui¹, Imane Halkhams², Rachid El Alami¹, Mohammed Ouazzani Jamil², Hassan Qjidaa²

¹LISAC Laboratory, Faculty of Sciences Dhar El Mahraz, Sidi Mohamed Ben Abdellah University, Fez, Morocco

²SIEDD Laboratory, Private University of Fez (UPF), Fez, Morocco

Article Info

Article history:

Received Mar 13, 2024

Revised Feb 19, 2025

Accepted Mar 11, 2025

Keywords:

Ansyes high frequency structure simulator

Microstrip antenna

Multiband antenna

Slot

Terahertz antenna

ABSTRACT

The rapid evolution of terahertz (THz) technology has fueled an increasing demand for efficient, compact, and adaptable antennas that can function for a number of frequency bands in the THz spectral regime. This research outlines the analyses and design process of a multiband antenna for THz applications. Initially, an antenna with a single frequency band is created without any slot, with its lower resonant mode functions at a singular frequency of 171 GHz. To achieve multiband functionality, various rectangular slots can be added into the microstrip antenna's radiating element. The suggested structure is constructed on a polyimide substrate, while its radiating elements are crafted from copper, with a compact size of $1.4 \times 1.1 \times 0.14$ mm. It can achieve a reflection coefficient of -30.38 dB, -33.37 dB, and -19.33 dB at 123 GHz, 168 GHz, and 182 GHz, respectively. Furthermore, the antenna yields favorable gains at the respective frequencies, measuring 3.97 dB, 4.34 dB, and 5.66 dB for 0.123, 0.168, and 0.182 THz respectively. Additionally, the antenna demonstrates high efficiencies of 81.5%, 85%, and 91.2%, respectively. Hence, the suggested THz antenna will be useful for surveillance radar (123 GHz), medical imaging (168 GHz), and radio astronomy (182 GHz) applications.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) license.

Corresponding Author:

Youssef Amraoui

LISAC Laboratory, Faculty of Sciences Dhar El Mahraz, Sidi Mohamed Ben Abdellah University
Fez, Morocco

Email: youssef.amraoui2@usmba.ac.ma

1. INTRODUCTION

Over the recent times, there has been a noticeable increase in the need for developing compact devices that can transmit and receive data at the utmost speeds while also conserving energy. The terahertz (THz) band occupies a vital but largely unexplored domain in the realm of wireless communication technologies [1], [2]. This frequency range typically encompasses frequencies spanning from 0.1 THz to 10000 GHz (Wavelength ranging from 3 mm to 30 μ m), which aligns with the infrared range in the shorter wavelengths and transitions into the millimeter wave region in the longer wavelength spectrum [3], [4]. The advantages of the THz band encompass attributes such as exceptional spatial resolution, rapid high-speed communication, low power consumption, ultra-wideband capabilities, and efficient high-data-rate transmission [5], [6]. Due to its distinctive characteristics, the THz band holds promise for different applications in fields such as biomedical applications [7], imaging [8], communication [9], and spectroscopy [10]. However, the THz band encounters emerging concerns, including significant signal attenuation and path loss attributed to water and molecular absorption within the atmosphere [11]. The antenna stands as a pivotal component in the THz band, and among the different THz antennas available, microstrip antennas are highly regarded for their suitability in THz applications [12]. They are favored due to their cost-effectiveness,

lightweight nature, compatible with integrated circuit technology, and ease of manufacture and design. Nevertheless, it's important to acknowledge that conventional patch antennas operating at frequencies face certain challenges, including issues with low gain, subpar radiation performance, and limited bandwidth [13]. Over the past few years, numerous microstrip antenna variants have developed, encompassing stacked, slotted T-type configurations, as well as both single-band and multi-band designs [14]. To ensure the efficient utilization of available spectrum, communication systems demand antennas that combine compact size with the ability of working over several frequency bands. These multiband antennas are engineered to function effectively over many frequency ranges, with different parts of the antenna designed to be responsive to distinct bands [15].

Attaining multiband resonance in antenna operating within the THz spectrum has presented a multifaceted challenge, leading researchers to explore a variety of methods to achieve this capability. Common techniques include the utilization of metamaterials [16], frequency-selective surfaces (FSS) [17], fractal antenna [18], and the incorporation of slots. The best strategy to use will rely on the particular requirements of the application because each of these approaches has a different set of benefits and drawbacks. For this paper, the utilization of a slotting technique has been adopted, incorporating slots into the patch structure to achieve multiband frequencies. This approach offers the distinct advantage of providing versatile resonance characteristics across the entire THz spectrum while preserving the compactness and integration potential necessary for modern THz applications. The primary objective of employing the slotted technique in this paper is to attain multiple operating frequencies across different bands.

Numerous THz multiband antennas have been suggested in the literature [15], [18]-[21]. The antenna [18] has a total area of $700 \times 900 \text{ mm}^2$ and has three resonant frequencies, 1.04, 0.984, and 0.948 THz, with a 9 dB realized gain at the 0.948 THz resonating frequency. The outcome and performance suggest that the suggested antenna will work well with monolithic microwave integrated circuit (MMIC) and small wireless devices. Vijayalakshmi *et al.* [19] presents a tri-band antenna array designed multiple input/multiple output (MIMO) for THz communications. The antenna provides an impressive performance with a 10 dB return loss bandwidth of 60, 43, and 38 GHz, centered at frequencies of 4.5, 3.2, and 2.3 THz, respectively. Additionally, the antenna realizes gains greater than 5 dBi for each of these working frequencies. Krishna *et al.* [15], a self-similar two parasitic components are inserted close to the patch to give multiple resonances. A rogers RT material is used to incorporate a multi-band THz antenna that is biased on a very thin sheet of graphene that serves as a radiating element and has a thickness of 0.5 nm. With radiation efficiencies of 93.73%, 83.87%, 94.14%, 87.25%, 88.8%, and 90.16% at corresponding resonant frequencies, this antenna operates at 7.96, 7.45, 6.64, 6.28, 5.86 and 3.58 THz. Nissiyah and Madhan [20], the straightforward graphene-based patch antenna's performance is improved by allowing it to function at higher frequency ranges in order to achieve quad and triple band resonances. The antenna is made to work on the triple band (2.01, 2.74, 4.52) and the quad band (1.73, 2.6, 4.01, 4.72). To investigate the resonance properties and radiation patterns, the chemical potential of the surface plasmons is changed from 2 to 0 eV. At 4.41 THz, the triple band operation achieves a directivity of 3.66 dBi and gain of 1.22 dB. At 4.72, 4.01, 2.6, and 1.73 THz, quad band operation is also accomplished, with a directivity of 7.17 dBi and gain of 1.61 dB. Shalini and Madhan [21], the slot has been adjusted in order to allow the antenna to work at two distinct frequencies: 4.83 and 1.96 THz, each with a bandwidth of 100 and 80 GHz, respectively. Additionally, the antenna delivers a sizable gain of 4.3 and 4.75 dB across the operational bands. Furthermore, by creating defects in the ground plane, the antenna is able to operate in three bands at 5.55, 4.83, and 1.96 THz. The inclusion of a slot inside the radiator stands out as a powerful and effective way to introduce a number of modes into the antenna, facilitating its multi-band functioning and concurrently improving the antenna's impedance qualities. Our method seeks to address the difficulties related to THz frequency antenna design. Thus, a new tri band slotted antenna for THz applications is analyzed and designed in this research. To boost the recommended antenna's performance, enhancements were implemented through the incorporation of a combination of rectangular and semicircular slots onto the patch. In the study, many physical characteristics of the suggested antenna are analyzed.

The following list of major contributions and performance metrics is provided in the manuscript: i) a compact tri band of a THz antenna; ii) high-efficiency multiband THz antenna, and it exhibits conventional performance characteristics compared to previously reported THz patch antennas in literature; iii) the slotted antenna structure is very straightforward, making it easy to fabricate and suitable for THz systems; iv) the recommended antenna sustains a radiation efficiency exceeding 80% across the resonating frequency range; and v) the presented multiband antenna functions with mean gains of 3.97 dB, 4.34 dB, and 5.66 dB across its operating frequency bands.

2. THEORY AND DESIGN APPROACH

This work suggests a tri-band microstrip antenna design for THz applications with an overall substrate area of $1 \times 1.5 \times 0.14 \text{ mm}^3$, as depicted in Figure 1. The antenna's radiating components are printed on top of a polyimide substrate with a loss tangent of 0.008 and a relative permittivity of 3.5. Various rectangular and semicircular slots varying in length (L), but with the same width (w) and same radius (r) are printed in the radiating element (patch) as shown in Figure 1(a). Utilizing the finite element method based ansys high frequency structure simulator, the design and simulation processes were carried out. With a central feed of width W_f and length L_f , the antenna is stimulated in this configuration by a microstrip transmission line technique. The antenna's bottom view is observed in Figure 1(b). The conducting patch is the primary component of a microstrip antenna that changes return loss, surface current distribution, bandwidth, impedance matching, and radiation pattern to modify antenna performance. In the current research, the radiating patch's performance was enhanced through the implementation of slotting techniques. This study's uniqueness is attained through the implementation of patch modifications aimed at enhancing the current distributions on the antenna's surface. For more details in the design approach see reference [22].

Figure 1. Tri band antenna design in HFSS; (a) the top view and (b) the rear view

The equations available in the literature simplify the calculation of radiating element dimensions, as in [23]. The width (W_p) of the microstrip antenna is expressed in (1) for efficient radiation. Accounting for the fringing effect, where electromagnetic waves partially travel through the dielectric material and partially through the air, an effective dielectric constant (ϵ_{reff}) is introduced in (2). Due to these fringing effects, the electrical length exceeds the physical dimensions, and (ΔL) the extended electrical length of the patch can be calculated utilizing (3). Where in (4) is employed to calculate the patch's length (L_p), and (5) is used to calculate the wavelength. In these equations, C represents the speed of light in a vacuum, f_r is the resonant frequency, and ϵ_e represents the dielectric constant. The width w_f is found using (6) and (7). By using these equations, the parameters of the suggested antenna are summarized in Table 1.

$$W_p = \frac{c}{2f_r} \sqrt{\frac{2}{\epsilon_r + 1}} \quad (1)$$

$$\epsilon_{reff} = \frac{-1 + \epsilon_r}{2} \times \frac{1}{\sqrt{\frac{h}{w} \times 12 + 1}} + \frac{1 + \epsilon_r}{2} \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta L = \frac{(0.3 + \epsilon_e)}{(\epsilon_e - 0.258)} \times \frac{(\frac{w}{h} + 0.262)}{(0.813 + \frac{w}{h})} \times h \times 0.412 \quad (3)$$

$$L_p = -2\Delta L + \frac{c}{f_r \times 2 \times \sqrt{\epsilon_e}} \quad (4)$$

$$\lambda = \frac{c}{f_r} \tag{5}$$

$$\frac{wf}{h} = \begin{cases} 8e^A \times \frac{1}{e^{2A}-2} ; \text{if } 2 \geq \frac{w}{h} \\ \frac{\epsilon_r-1}{2\epsilon_r} \left[\ln(B-1) - \frac{0.61}{\epsilon_r} + 0.39 \right] + 2 \times \frac{1}{\pi} \left\{ B-1 - \ln(-1+2B) \right\}; \text{if } 2 \leq \frac{w}{h} \end{cases} \tag{6}$$

$$A = \left(0.23 + 0.11 \times \frac{1}{\epsilon_r} \right) \times \frac{\epsilon_r-1}{\epsilon_r+1} + \sqrt{\frac{\epsilon_r+1}{2}} \times 2\pi \times \frac{Z_0}{Z_f} \tag{7}$$

Z_f is the wave impedance in free space, while Z_0 is the characteristic impedance.

Table 1. The size specifications of the recommended antenna (mm)

Dimensions	Value	Dimensions	Value	Dimensions	Value
Lg	1.5	Wg	1	r	0.05
Lp	0.7	wp	0.8	L4	0.3
Lf	0.67	wf	0.08	L3	0.5
L1	0.4	w1	0.1	w3	0.10
L2	0.7	w2	0.10	w4	0.1

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A study was conducted to understand and illustrate the influence of the parameters of the tri band antenna. This study used a parameter-centric technique, systematically varying one parameter at a time while maintaining the others intact, to identify the ideal antenna size and performance. In Figure 2, the return loss in the lower, middle, and higher frequency bands may be varied by varying the values of w_4 , L_4 , and w_3 . Figure 2(a) exhibits the effect of changing the value of w_4 from 0.05 to 0.15 mm. It can be noticed that the increase in the value of w_4 shifts the resonant frequencies from 123 to 120.8 GHz, 169 GHz to 167 GHz, and 184 GHz to 180.5 GHz in the lower, center, and higher frequency bands, with a rise in S_{11} . Figure 2(b) also shows that the lower band shifted from 124 GHz to 123 GHz when the values of the L_4 increased from 0.1 to 0.3 mm, while the middle band remained almost unchanged. The highest band decreased from 185 GHz to 182 GHz, with an increase in return loss in the lower and middle bands as shown in Figure 2(b). Changing the value of w_3 from 0.15 mm to 0.07 mm results in the upper frequency band shifting from 179 GHz to 181 GHz, while the middle band still unchangeable, and the lower band shifts from 123 to 121 GHz with an increase of S_{11} as presented in Figure 2(c). Thus, the suggested antenna’s best dimensions are $w_4=0.10$ mm, $L_4=0.3$ mm, and $w_3=0.10$ mm.

Figure 2. Parametric study of the antenna fluctuation in; (a) ‘ w_4 ’, (b) ‘ L_4 ’, and (c) ‘ w_3 ’

The recommended antenna design’s procedure is shown in this section. The suggested antenna starts with a rectangular patch as displayed in Figure 3 (Ant I) with a - 10 dB bandwidth of 5.6 GHz ($S_{11} = -15.20$ dB) but in this instance, the antenna is working only at 171 GHz frequency as appears in Figure 3. Then, to shift the frequency towards the multiband, different rectangular slots are introduced onto the patch of initial rectangular patch, as depicted in Figure 3 (Ant II). The S_{11} response of the second step (Ant II) reveals a tri-band with resonance at 124 GHz, 171 GHz (the fundamental frequency), and 185 GHz frequencies with a

reflection coefficient of -15.57 dB (3.04 GHz), -35.85 dB (5.9 GHz), and -20.92 dB (11.98 GHz) respectively as shown in Figure 3. Finally, in the third case (Ant III), various semicircular slots are added on the radiating element as presented in Figure 3 (suggested antenna). When the semicircular slots are used (Ant III), there is a change in the lower frequency from 124 to 123 GHz although, with excellent return loss ($S_{11} = -30.38$ dB) at the same time, while the middle frequency shifted from 171 GHz to 168 GHz ($S_{11} = -33.37$ dB), with a bandwidth of 5.6 GHz. Similarly, the upper frequency is changed from 185 GHz to 182 GHz ($S_{11} = -19.33$ dB) as depicted in Figure 3. Thus, it can be noted that the recommended antenna is a viable option for multiband THz applications.

Additionally, a simulation of the standing wave ratio (SWR) will be employed to describe and evaluate the suggested antenna. Since the SWR value controls how well the antenna adapts, if the voltage standing wave ratio (VSWR) value is less than 2 dB, the antenna will be perfectly adapted [22]. As presented in Figure 4(a), the recommended antenna has an SWR of 1.07 dB, 1.06 dB, and 1.2 dB for the lower, middle, and higher frequency bands, respectively. Figure 4(b) displays a graph depicting the efficiency values at: 123 GHz, 168 GHz, and 182 GHz. At a frequency of 123 GHz, the efficiency is approximately 81.6%. At 168 GHz, the efficiency reaches 86.06%. Finally, at 182 GHz, the efficiency peaks at 91.17%. This figure illustrates how antenna efficiency varies with frequency, showcasing a gradual increase in efficiency as the frequency rises. The recommended antenna's radiation pattern is illustrated in Figure 5. Figure 5(a) to (f) depict the 3D and 2D antenna radiation pattern in H-plane and E-plane of the suggested THz antenna. A maximum gain of 4.34 dB at 168 GHz, 5.66 dB at 182 GHz, and 3.97 dB at 123 GHz is what the simulation results show for the recommended antenna.

The surface current distribution over the radiating patch is apparent in Figure 6 to help explain the multiband behavior of the recommended antenna employing different slots in the patch. In Figures 6(a) to (c) the resonating frequencies exhibit the highest current density within the transmission line and semicircular section.

Figure 3. Comparison of S_{11} simulation results for the recommended antenna design processes

Figure 4. SWR and radiation efficiency of the recommended antenna: (a) SWR and (b) radiation efficiency

Figure 5. Simulated far-fields radiation pattern in 3D and 2D at; (a) 123 GHz, (b) 123 GHz, (c) 168 GHz, (d) 168 GHz, and (e) 182 GHz, and (f) 182 GHz

Figure 6. Surface current distribution of suggested antenna at; (a) 123 GHz, (b) 168 GHz, and (c) 182 GHz

Table 2 offers a comparative analysis between the recommended antenna and other antennas documented in the existing literature. Notably, the recommended antenna stands out by offering a tri-band response within the THz spectrum. It's crucial to emphasize that while enhancing the performance of a single-band antenna can be relatively straightforward, achieving such improvements in a multi-band antenna is a notably challenging task, and this accomplishment is a significant achievement highlighted in the research work being reported. The antenna presented in [20], [24], [25] operates at the multi-band frequency but has poor gain and a smaller S11 compared to our antenna. The antennas mentioned in [26], [27] have some good performance, but they operate at a single band. Additionally, it should be highlighted that the

application of the suggested method offers a simpler solution when contrasted with other strategies involving graphene or alterations in substrate height. When considering the comparison table, it becomes evident that the suggested technique outperforms existing methods documented in the literature. This advantage is especially notable when it comes to applying the technique to design a dual-band antenna, where other approaches may pose challenges or complexities. finally, compared to the other antennas, the suggested antenna performs far better.

Table 2. Comparison of the suggested and previously documented designs

	Frequency band (THz)	Gain (dB)	Radiation efficiency (%)	Technique	S11 (dB)
[24]	2.48; 3.35	2.7 dBi 6.2	87.3 53.47	Varying substrate height	-17 -22
[25]	2.17 2.59	4.01 5.03	64.12 60.8	Graphene	-28 -35
[20]	1.81; 2.64; 4.41	1; 1.03; 1.22	-	Graphene	-17.51; -22.08; -10.56
[26]	1	2.45 dBi	44	Single	-24
[27]	0.72	-	-	Single	-59.97
This work	123; 168; 182	3.97; 4.34; 5.66	81.5; 85; 91.2	Slotted	-30.38; -33.37; -19.33

4. CONCLUSION

In the present research, a tri-band antenna with varied slots in the radiating element (patch) is employed for THz applications. The suggested antenna exhibits resonance at 123 GHz, 168 GHz, and 182 GHz with return losses of -30.38 dB, -33.37 dB, and -19.33 dB, respectively. $SWR < 2$ is attained in all frequency ranges. At lower, medium, and higher band frequencies, the antenna, with 81.5%, 85%, and 91.2% radiation efficiency, respectively, produces a considerable gain of 3.97 dB, 4.34 dB, and 5.66 dB. The gain, bandwidth, reflection coefficient, and radiation efficiency of this antenna were much higher than those of comparable antennas. Thus, this antenna can serve as an effective solution for surveillance radar, medical imaging, and radio astronomy applications. In order to further improve data transmission capacity and system reliability in these frequency ranges, this research also sets the path for future improvements in integrating MIMO systems.

FUNDING INFORMATION

This research was supported by private University of Fez and Sidi Mohamed Ben Abdellah university

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS STATEMENT

This journal uses the Contributor Roles Taxonomy (CRediT) to recognize individual author contributions, reduce authorship disputes, and facilitate collaboration.

Name of Author	C	M	So	Va	Fo	I	R	D	O	E	Vi	Su	P	Fu
Youssef Amraoui	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓				✓
Imane Halkhams			✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓
Rachid El Alami	✓		✓	✓			✓			✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Mohammed Ouazzani	✓			✓			✓			✓	✓		✓	✓
Jamil														
Hassan Qjidaa	✓			✓			✓			✓	✓		✓	✓

C : Conceptualization

M : Methodology

So : Software

Va : Validation

Fo : Formal analysis

I : Investigation

R : Resources

D : Data Curation

O : Writing - Original Draft

E : Writing - Review & Editing

Vi : Visualization

Su : Supervision

P : Project administration

Fu : Funding acquisition

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data will be made available on request.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. E. Benlakehal, A. Hocini, D. Khedrouche, M. N. Temmar, T. A. Denidni, and I. Shayea, "Design and analysis of a 1×2 microstrip patch antenna array based on photonic crystals with a graphene load in THZ," *Journal of Optics*, vol. 52, no. 2, pp. 483-493, 2023, doi: 10.1007/s12596-022-01006-8.
- [2] J. K. Rai, U. Patel, P. Tiwari, P. Ranjan, and R. Chowdhury, "Machine Learning Enabled Compact Frequency-Tunable Triple-Band Hexagonal-Shaped Graphene Antenna for THz Communication," *International Journal of Communication Systems*, vol. 38, no. 1, p. e6044, 2025, doi: 10.1002/dac.6044.
- [3] S. Yao and W. Lei, "Design and review of terahertz antennas," *Applied and Computational Engineering*, vol. 73, pp. 280-287, 2024, doi: 10.54254/2755-2721/73/20240412.
- [4] Y. Amraoui, I. Halkhams, R. El Alami, M. O. Jamil, and H. Qjidaa, "A new approach to designing a multiband antenna using photonic crystals and load graphene for terahertz application," *Results in Engineering*, vol. 22, p. 102327, 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.rineng.2024.102327.
- [5] L. Moni, M. S. R. Zishan, S. H. Eshan, and R. R. Hasan, "Graphene based terahertz patch antenna for breast tumor detection," *TELKOMNIKA (Telecommunication Computing Electronics and Control)*, vol. 22, no. 5, pp. 1073-1082, 2024, doi: 10.12928/TELKOMNIKA.v22i5.26077.
- [6] J. H. Nirob *et al.*, "Optimized tri-band MIMO antenna design for 6G terahertz applications and future connectivity," *TELKOMNIKA (Telecommunication Computing Electronics and Control)*, vol. 23, no. 2, pp. 553-562, 2025, doi: 10.12928/TELKOMNIKA.v23i2.26579.
- [7] B. S. M. Bokhari, M. Bhagyaveni, and R. Rajkumar, "On the use of graphene for quad-band THz microstrip antenna array with diversity reception for biomedical applications," *Applied Physics A*, vol. 127, no. 6, p. 467, 2021, doi: 10.1007/s00339-021-04616-4.
- [8] I. Malhotra and G. Singh, "Terahertz Terahertz (THz) Antenna Technology for Imaging Imaging and Sensing Sensing Applications," in *Terahertz Antenna Technology for Imaging and Sensing Applications*: Springer, 2021, pp. 75-102.
- [9] S. Fakhte and M. M. Taskhiri, "Graphene-based terahertz antenna with polarization reconfiguration," *Physica Scripta*, vol. 98, no. 11, 2023, doi: 10.1088/1402-4896/ad03ca.
- [10] G. Singh, K. S. Sandha, and A. Kansal, "GA based optimized graphene antenna design for detection of explosives and drugs using THz spectroscopy," *Micro and Nanostructures*, vol. 179, p. 207566, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.micrna.2023.207566.
- [11] R. Pant and L. Malviya, "THz antennas design, developments, challenges, and applications: A review," *International Journal of Communication Systems*, vol. 36, no. 8, p. e5474, 2023, doi: 10.1002/dac.5474.
- [12] M. E. Benlakehal, A. Hocini, D. Khedrouche, M. N. e. Temmar, and T. A. Denidni, "Gain enhancement of a novel 1×2 microstrip patch antenna array based on cylindrical and cuboid photonic crystal substrate in THz," *Analog Integrated Circuits and Signal Processing*, vol. 114, no. 1, pp. 159-170, 2023, doi: 10.1007/s10470-023-02134-2.
- [13] P. R. Pandya, M. S. Devi, and N. Langhnoja, "Terahertz Antennas—Review and Design," *Terahertz Devices, Circuits and Systems: Materials, Methods and Applications*, pp. 305-317, 2022, doi: 10.1007/978-981-19-4105-4_18.
- [14] Y. He, Y. Chen, L. Zhang, S.-W. Wong, and Z. N. Chen, "An overview of terahertz antennas," *China Communications*, vol. 17, no. 7, pp. 124-165, 2020, doi: 10.23919/JCC.2020.07.011.
- [15] C. M. Krishna, N. Suguna, R. SaravanaKumar, S. A. alias Rajasree, V. P. Ponnappalli, and M. Subbareddy, "Giuseppe peano fractal loaded multiband antenna using parasitic strips for THz applications," *Materials Today: Proceedings*, vol. 66, pp. 3675-3682, 2022.
- [16] A. Y. Ashyap *et al.*, "Multi-Band Metamaterial Antenna for Terahertz Applications," *Computers, Materials & Continua*, vol. 75, no. 1, pp. 1765-1782, 2023, doi: 10.32604/cmc.2023.030618.
- [17] P. Das and G. Varshney, "Gain enhancement of dual-band terahertz antenna using reflection-based frequency selective surfaces," *Optical and Quantum Electronics*, vol. 54, no. 3, p. 161, 2022, doi: 10.1007/s11082-022-03548-4.
- [18] S. Vijay, J. Ali, P. Yupapin, B. H. Ahmad, and K. Ray, "A triband EBG loaded microstrip fractal antenna for THz application," *Scientia Iranica*, vol. 30, no. 1, pp. 207-217, 2023, doi: 10.24200/SCI.2021.57076.5053.
- [19] K. Vijayalakshmi, C. S. K. Selvi, and B. Sapna, "Novel tri-band series fed microstrip antenna array for THz MIMO communications," *Optical and Quantum Electronics*, vol. 53, pp. 1-13, 2021, doi: 10.1007/s11082-021-03065-w.
- [20] G. J. Nissiyah and M. G. Madhan, "Graphene based microstrip antenna for triple and quad band operation at terahertz frequencies," *Optik*, vol. 231, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.ijleo.2021.166360.
- [21] M. Shalini and M. G. Madhan, "Performance predictions of slotted graphene patch antenna for multi-band operation in terahertz regime," *Optik*, vol. 204, p. 164223, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.ijleo.2020.164223.
- [22] A. Youssef, I. Halkhams, R. El Alami, M. O. Jamil, and H. Qjidaa, "Innovative flexible and compact patch antenna for multiband terahertz applications," *Scientific African*, vol. 24, p. e02196, 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.sciaf.2024.e02196.
- [23] M. Krishna Ch, T. Islam, N. Suguna, S. V. Kumari, R. D. H. Devi, and S. Das, "A micro-scaled graphene-based wideband (0.57–1.02 THz) patch antenna for terahertz applications," *Results in Optics*, vol. 12, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.rio.2023.100501.
- [24] J. N. George and M. G. Madhan, "Analysis of single band and dual band graphene based patch antenna for terahertz region," *Physica E: low-dimensional systems and nanostructures*, vol. 94, pp. 126-131, 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.physe.2017.08.001.
- [25] S. Mrunalini and A. Manoharan, "Dual-band re-configurable graphene-based patch antenna in terahertz band for wireless network-on-chip applications," *IET Microwaves, Antennas & Propagation*, vol. 11, no. 14, pp. 2104-2108, 2017, doi: 10.1049/iet-map.2017.0415.
- [26] M.-R. Nickpay, M. Danaie, and A. Shahzadi, "Wideband rectangular double-ring nanoribbon graphene-based antenna for terahertz communications," *IETE Journal of Research*, vol. 68, no. 3, pp. 1625-1634, 2022, doi: 10.1080/03772063.2019.1661801.
- [27] S. Shamim, M. S. Uddin, M. R. Hasan, and M. Samad, "Design and implementation of miniaturized wideband microstrip patch antenna for high-speed terahertz applications," *Journal of Computational Electronics*, vol. 20, pp. 604-610, 2021, doi: 10.1007/s10825-020-01587-2.

BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Youssef Amraoui born in Morocco, in February 1997. He obtained his Master's degree in Microelectronics from the Faculty of Science Dhar EL Mahraz Fez Morocco, in 2021. He is now a Ph.D. student in Laboratory of Computer Science, Signals, Automation and Cognitivism (LISAC), Faculty of Sciences Dhar El Mehraz, Sidi Mohamed Ben Abdellah University Fez. He can be contacted at email: youssef.amraoui2@usmba.ac.ma.

Imane Halkhams born in 1988 in Fez, Morocco. She received her Ph.D. in Microelectronics from the University of Sidi Mohammed Ben Abdellah, 2017. She also received her Engineering degree in Networks and Telecommunications from the National School of Applied Sciences of Fez in 2012. Currently, she is a Professor at the Engineering Science Faculty of UPF. She can be contacted at email: imane.halkhams@usmba.ac.ma.

Rachid El Alami is a Professor in Department of Physics, FSDM, USMBA, Fez, Morocco. He received his BS. degree in Electronics from Polydisciplinary Faculty of Taza, the MS and Ph.D. degrees in Signals, Systems and Informatics in FSDM, USMBA, Fez, Morocco, in 2008 and 2013 respectively. His research interests include the channel coding/decoding (LDPC codes), FPGA implementation and image processing. He can be contacted at email: rachid.elalami@usmba.ac.ma.

Mohammed Ouazzani Jamil is currently a Professor in Private University of Fez (UPF). He does research in condensed matter physics, hamiltonian system, chaos, renewable energy and artificial intelligence. Their current project is dynamic systems. He can be contacted at email: Ouazzani@upf.ac.ma.

Hassan Qjidaa is now a Professor in Department of Physics, FSDM, USMBA, Fez, Morocco. He received his Master degree since 1984 and Ph.D. degrees since 1987 in Electrical Engineering from Nuclear Physics Institute of Lyon, France. His research interests include Li-Ion battery charger interface (BCI) and BMS, RFID passive and active tags, CMOS mixed mode integrated circuit design, Integrated Class-D power output stage, renewable energy and image processing. He can be contacted at email: qjidah@yahoo.fr.